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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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8	D8.5	D40	Report on barriers and opportunities on R&I impact-driven agendas #2	UPV/EHU

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Report	Public	D37 D38 D39

Description (short)
Building upon former D39, this deliverable responds to a triple objective: (1) it reports on the different workshops, encounters, webinars, surveys, mapping exercises, and meetings that served the collection and subsequent analysis of the barriers and opportunities for research impact-driven agendas from month 25 (September 2023) to month 36 (August 2024); (2) presents the results of the analysis of the different collected barriers, challenges, and opportunities to implement impact-driven research agendas; (3) and proposes good practices and solutions to address the identified challenges.

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INTRODUCTION

ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT RISE

ENLIGHT is a European University Alliance to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability and global engagement through Higher Education Transformation. ENLIGHT brings together nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries (University of the Basque Country, University of Bordeaux, Comenius University Bratislava, University of Galway (formerly National University of Ireland, Galway), Ghent University, University of Göttingen, University of Groningen, University of Tartu, Uppsala University). In the new phase of ENLIGHT (ENLIGHT 2.0, 2023-2027), the University of Bern joined the alliance which strengthens the diversity and impact of the alliance, furthering its mission to develop a university of the future.

ENLIGHT obtained funding from the European Commission in the Horizon 2020 *Science with and For Society* (SwafS) work programme for the **ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society)**, which seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, **ENLIGHT RISE** deploys a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The ENLIGHT RISE project is structured around nine major Work Packages, of which Work Package (WP) 8 is focused on Impact. **The main objective of WP8 is to promote an impact-driven research and innovation agenda.** WP8 explores the frontiers of a common impact-driven R&I agenda (task 8.1), by:

- Collecting and analyzing the opportunities and barriers encountered to implement this agenda (8.1.3);
- Developing actions to promote a culture of R&I impact within ENLIGHT universities (8.1.1); and
- By reviewing methods and good practices of impact assessment and measurement worldwide (8.1.2).

Additionally, WP8 facilitates further impact knowledge sharing with other European University Alliances as part of the FOREU2 impact thematic group, to spread and share solutions, successful practices, identified barriers and challenges, as well as cooperation formats and models (Task 8.2).

WP8 is led by University of the Basque Country, with co-leads University of Galway and Ghent University. The primary focus of WP8 is the concept of "Research Impact", as distinct from R&I impact. As one of the first consensuses, WP8 leaders with the partner university representatives agreed on the following definition of research impact as ***the effects of research in the real world. Impact is the changes we can see (demonstrate, measure, capture), beyond academia (in society, economy, environment) which happen because of our research (caused by, contributed to, attributable to).***

The report on barriers and opportunities for impact-driven research agendas

In line with the overall objectives of Task 8.1.3 above mentioned, this Deliverable **collects and analyses barriers and opportunities encountered to implement a common impact-driven R&I agenda.** This document is a continuation of former Deliverable 39 presented in August 2023 and covers the period from September 2023 to August 2024. More specifically, it presents:

1. **All sources that have been used during the last year to collect the barriers, challenges and opportunities to implement impact-driven research agendas**, in the form of a research impact landscaping exercise; through the ENLIGHT self-assessment toolkit;

workshops, encounters, webinars and other public events; ENLIGHT workshop “what makes research impact so challenging?”; ENLIGHT research impact training; FOREU2 impact thematic group meetings and workshop (first chapter).

2. **The results of the analysis on the collected barriers, challenges, and opportunities to implement impact-driven research agendas** (second chapter).
3. **Good practices and solutions to address the identified challenges, including ENLIGHT actions planned to be taken in the short and medium-term** (third chapter).

This report considers barriers and opportunities for both *impact-driven research agendas at universities institutional level*, and for *common impact-driven research agendas among different institutions*.

1. Data Collection Sources

1.1. Research Impact Landscaping Exercise

During the initial development phase of WP8, the impact team posed 3 key questions to each partner University to gauge their understanding and implementation of R&I impact policies and practices (November-December 2021). The 2021 exercise included the following questions:

- **Question 1 - What is your understanding of R&I Impact?**
- **Question 2 - Does your university have a R&I Impact policy/ implementation plan? If so, could you please give more information about it?**
- **Question 3 - Independently of the response to the previous question, could you please identify (a) good R&I Impact practice(s) in your university?**

To get an updated overview and see if any changes were made in the ENLIGHT Universities R&I Impact landscape, the exercise was relaunched in April 2024, asking 'does the 2021 response remain valid? and provide any revisions or amendments'.

Figure 1 gives an overview of the responses from the 2024 Research Impact Landscape exercise:

UPDATE OVERVIEW OF ENLIGHT UNIVERSITIES R&I IMPACT LANDSCAPE			
ENLIGHT University	1. Definition of Impact	2. Institutional Impact Policy/Implementation Plan	3. Good Practices
Tartu	YES – no change on response	YES – Impact is embedded in strategic plan and emphasis will likely be on impact in the next strategic plan.	YES – Tartu have established the Centre for Sustainable Development in 2022, analysing societal challenges, using concepts & methods from different disciplines.
Bordeaux	YES – agree with WP8 definition but differentiate between planned impact at the beginning of a project and impact which can be measured at the end.	NO – still no policy however the launch of several actions such as 'impact project' providing methodological kit on impact assessment.	YES – projects with impact requirements, guide with impact vocabulary is planned, methodological guide for impact pathway, methodological guide to impact assessment are all planned.
Groningen	YES - still using SEP 2021-2027 & strategic plan 2021-2026 as framework	Since 2021, the Research & Impact cluster has been further developed. Situated at the core of the university, the cluster contributes to university-wide policy, provides advice to the board, and supports faculties and researchers. The cluster's goal is to ensure that the RUG excels in research and maximizes the societal impact of its research.	YES - currently making an inventory of practices across the faculties. One example is the recent start of the Theory of Change workshop for researchers applying for large grants. We plan to extend this workshop to include public-private partnership collaborations and innovation grant applicants
Galway	YES – European Commission definition of Research Impact. Distinction between academic & non-academic impact.	YES – embedded in both institution strategic planned and R&I strategy. Impact is central to the Institutional Review of Research Performance and developing impact case studies.	YES – remains valid and adding in a Research Impact Seminar Series since July 2023.
UGent	YES – REF definition still good but mostly use a variation of Julie Bailey's version	YES – still in place and administrative & policy levels undergoing restructure creating opportunities to rethink policy & impact support structure	YES – with additions: develop new assessment framework for interdisciplinary research consortia aimed at societal impact / expansion of research info system & research explorer / specific strategy creation / Doctoral schools training on socio-economic impact / integrating impact in Global Minds Fund
Comenius	NO – response is the same as previous, no set definition but agrees with WP8 definition	NO – not yet a R&I Impact policy, but institutional guidelines will be prepared later 2024	YES – Impactful research and knowledge transfer
Uppsala	NO – response is the same as previous, no definition but agrees with WP8 definition. R&I Impact understanding varies across the university.	NO – difficult to implement due to decentralisation of research domains.	YES – impactful research and innovation projects, using tools to promote researchers to use their research for innovation and impact
UPV/EHU	NO – agrees with WP8 definition	NO – impact is embedded in UPV/EHU 2030 agenda, and creation of a social impact office to spread impact culture throughout university	YES – remains valid. Also conducting studies aiming at measuring social impact of the institution.

Figure 1 Overview of Impact Landscaping Exercise June 2024 ENLIGHT WP8. From Deliverable 38.

The results from this second iteration and update to the Impact Landscaping Exercise demonstrated that although there was still some **disparity in the Institutional recognition of Research Impact** among the ENLIGHT Universities there was certainly **a shift in thinking and a move towards conformity, with a growing “institutionalisation” of research impact and targeted actions to promote a culture of impact at ENLIGHT universities.**

1.2. ENLIGHT Self-Assessment Toolkit for Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness

The [ENLIGHT Toolkit](#) is a self-reflection tool designed for universities to explore their research impact awareness, literacy and readiness at an institutional level. The toolkit guides users through focus areas considered as relevant for universities to be research impact-driven (figure 2). It is not a benchmarking tool but a diagnostic aid to identify areas of strength and opportunities for improvement in the research impact environment¹.

Figure 2. The 6 self-assessment dimensions of the ENLIGHT Toolkit. Available at <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/self-assessment>

Published in February 2023, and officially launched at the first [ENLIGHT Impact Conference](#) (29-30 March 2023), the toolkit is primarily targeted at members of management staff, academics and research support staff of ENLIGHT partner universities, but is also open to all interested users free of charge.

Up to 24 June 2024 (time of this report drafting), a total of **378 responses** were collected from both ENLIGHT partner universities and non-ENLIGHT organisations, as follows:

University	TOTAL	Member of Management Staff	Academic/ Research Staff	Research Support Staff
University de Bordeaux	60	4	37	19
Ghent University	17	-	8	9
Comenius University Bratislava	9	-	7	2
UPV/EHU	164	7	152	5
University of Galway	66	2	54	10
University of Göttingen	3	1	2	-
University of Groningen	16	1	6	9
University of Tartu	16	-	12	4
Uppsala University	7	-	6	1
Others	20	3	6	11
TOTAL	378	18	290	70

Figure 3. ENLIGHT Toolkit ENLIGHT Toolkit for Self-Assessment of Universities Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness respondent numbers (24 June 2024).

¹ For more information about the toolkit design, structure and content, please consult ENLIGHT RISE Deliverables D37 and D38.

Even though the level of engagement of ENLIGHT university staff has fallen compared to the first survey in 2022 (cfr. Deliverable 39) which may denote a **certain survey and/or impact fatigue**, the volume of responses is considerable to identify the following conclusions:

Research Impact Awareness, Literacy & Readiness

MAIN CONCLUSIONS (I)

- 1. CLARITY**
The majority (79%) of respondents state they do know what RI is. However, like the first survey there are multiple interpretations of RI (in/beyond academia; science communication; KT and innovation (spin-offs, patents)).
- 2. CONTEXT**
Most respondents (82%) state RI plays a role within national/ regional research quality assessment, policy or frameworks.
- 3. COMMITMENT**

 - The majority (7/9) of ENLIGHT Universities said that RI is a strategic priority for their university; whilst RI is seen as a strategic priority by 64% of academic responders and 92% of research support staff
 - 8/9 of ENLIGHT Institutional survey responders say that the University will “Greatly prioritise” around RI in the coming 5 years.
 - 7/9 of ENLIGHT Institutional survey responders say there IS Institutional leadership in RI.
 - All of the ENLIGHT universities now state there are “incentive& reward structures for RI”.

Figure 4. ENLIGHT Toolkit for Self-Assessment of Universities Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness survey main conclusions 1. From Deliverable 38.

Research Impact Awareness, Literacy & Readiness

MAIN CONCLUSIONS (II)

- 4. CAPACITIES & RESOURCES**

 - 7 ENLIGHT Universities now have dedicated support and advice available on RI, previously only 2. Limited number of Universities (2) with Support & Advice for RI. 8 of the ENLIGHT Universities do have dedicated systems for RI.
 - The majority of researchers/RSO respondents state NOT following a methodology for RI.
 - 22% of respondents agree that their university offers support training in RI related skills. 42% of RSO state NEVER having participated in RI training.
- 5. CONNECTIVITY**
One third of researchers/RSO respondents state they DO WORK with other teams to support RI and 42% indicated that RI activities are only “possibly/partly” aligned with University’s strategy.
- 6. CO-CREATION**

 - The majority of researchers/RSO respondents (59%) state they do work with societal stakeholders in the framework of their RI activities.
 - The types of collaboration according to the researchers/RSO respondents is:
 - ❖ 8% = Collaboration as potential end users of the project results or in order to share and / or co-participate in the project’s dissemination tasks
 - ❖ 5% = Collaboration for data collection and/ or contrast of the project results
 - ❖ 6% = Co-design of the project, the societal stakeholders have participated in the definition of the project and its objectives
 - ❖ 8% = Co-creation throughout all phases of the project: design, implementation, preparation of results

Figure 5. ENLIGHT Toolkit for Self-Assessment of Universities Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness survey main conclusions 2. From Deliverable 38.

Contrary to the 2023 preliminary results, where there was a disparity in responses by type of user, the analysis of the 2024 responses in function of the responder profile allows to identify some common patterns. **Members of the universities’ management teams** identify as areas of strength the *favourable (research impact) context* and their *commitment to research impact* (in the first exercise it was the co-creation with societal stakeholders). The *connectivity* within the institution being the weakest area (in the first exercise, the clarity around the concept of impact was the weakest).

Figure 6. Overview of the “member of university management team” users’ responses by dimension.

A similar vision is shared amongst the **academics/researchers**, who identify the *favourable context*, but also *clarity around the concept of research impact* as the main areas of strength at their universities. The *connectivity and level organizational capacities and resources* of a university appear to be the weaker dimensions for researchers.

Figure 7. Overview of the researchers users’ responses by dimension.

Research support staff highlights *clarity around the concept of research impact* as the strongest area, followed by the *favourable context* and *institutional commitment*. *Connectivity* (extent to which the different university teams (e.g., research groups, support units, etc.) work together, how they connect to an overall strategy and how cohesive these relationships are) being the weakest one.

Figure 8. Overview of the research support staff users' responses by dimension.

1.3. Workshops, Encounters, Webinars and Other Public Events

WP8 members have established a permanent dialogue with both academics and non-academic staff, policy-makers, industry and relevant societal actors around the topic of research-impact driven universities, which has been consolidated in the period covered by this report (September 2023-October 2024). In that context they have participated in several conferences, workshops, encounters and webinars to not only present the ENLIGHT impact approach to impact but to also discuss with the different stakeholders, the barriers/ challenges and opportunities for research-impact driven agendas. More specifically, WP8 was represented at the:

- [II Forum of European Universities Alliances](#) (Barcelona, Spain, 14-15 September 2023), where Igor Campillo (UPV/EHU) participated as speaker in the *Thematic Session: Monitoring Framework for the European University Initiative* together with representatives of the European Commission and other University Alliances. Target group: policy-makers and other European University Alliances.
- [AESIS Societal Impact of Social Sciences, Humanities & Arts](#) (Cardiff, UK, 18-20 October 2023), where Esther de Smet (UGENT) participated as speaker in the parallel session: *Integrating Impact in an Institutional Strategy*. Target group: world-wide research impact experts.
- [ENLIGHT Public Engagement Webinar: Impact in Academia](#) (online, 25 January 2024). In an event organised by ENLIGHT RISE WP6, Igor Campillo and Glória Nunes Rodrigues (UPV/EHU) introduced the concept of impact, presented the ENLIGHT methodology for the impact assessment of university activities and discussed with participants how to embed an impact-driven culture at ENLIGHT universities and beyond. Target group: ENLIGHT community.
- [EARMA online event: Advancing Research Impact in Project Management](#) (online, 4 March 2024). In a joint online event organised by the EARMA thematic groups on Post Award Project

Management and Impact, Glória Nunes Rodrigues (UPV/EHU) presented ENLIGHT approach to impact and the different activities to promote a culture of research impact in and beyond the Alliance. Target group: European research managers and administrators.

- [EARMA Conference 2024: Where is RMA Going? The future of RMA in a Rapidly Changing World](#) (Odense, 23-25 April 2024), where Áine Mhic Thaidhg (University of Galway), Igor Campillo and Glória Nunes Rodrigues (UPV/EHU) participated in the multiple parallel sessions on impact-related subjects, including in the EARMA Impact Thematic Group meeting. Igor Campillo and Glória Nunes Rodrigues also presented the August 2023 report on Barriers & Opportunities for Impact-driven Research in the Pecha Kucha session on *Beyond Impact*. Target group: European research managers and administrators.
- [UIIN Annual Conference: Shaping the Future of Talent and Innovation](#) (Madrid, 27-29 May 2024). Glória Nunes Rodrigues (UPV/EHU) presented the ENLIGHT Methodology for Impact Assessment in the session *Uniting for Impact: European University Alliances in Action*, other European University Alliances (YUFE, E³UDRES², U!REKA SHIFT) were also respresented. Target group: world-wide experts on university-industry interaction, entrepreneurial and engaged universities and the future of higher education.
- [AESIS Conference Societal Impact of Scientific Research](#) (Dublin, 26-28 June 2024). Áine Mhic Thaidhg (University of Galway), Esther de Smet (Ghent University) and Igor Campillo (UPV/EHU) participated in the event as panellists. Áine Mhic Thaidhg and Esther de Smet together with Giovanna Lima from Erasmus University Rotterdam hosted the workshop *Impact Clinic*, offering a space for open exchange on challenges faced by impact agents in the hopes of providing community support and peer advice based on joint experience and expertise Igor Campillo presented ENLIGHT Research Impact Training programme in the session *Doctoral Education and Impact Training*. Target group: world-wide research impact experts.

Figure 9. Picture of Glória Nunes Rodrigues (left) and Igor Campillo (right) from UPV/EHU, presenting *Barriers & Opportunities for Impact-driven Research in the in the Pecha Kucha session on Beyond Impact*. EARMA Conference 2024.

It is also worth mentioning the organisation by the University of Galway of the [Research Impact Series](#), which aim to tap into the expertise of national and international leaders in research impact. Through insightful discussions and the sharing of best practices from across the globe, the series aim to inspire researchers and the broader research community, both locally at University of Galway and globally. Áine Mhic Thaidhg (University of Galway. Organisation), Esther de Smet (Ghent University), Glória

Nunes Rodrigues (UPV/EHU) participated in the three sessions organised by the University of Galway in the period covered by this report (September 2023-August 2024):

- Presentation by Dr. David Phipps, “A personal, institutional and national approach to supporting the societal impact of research” (online, 24 October 2023).
- Presentation by Dr. Giovanna Lima, “Unlocking the challenge of communicating impact as a researcher” (online, 21 February 2024).
- Presentation by Dr. Julie Bayley, “Making a meaningful difference to society: an impact literate approach” (online, 14 April 2024).

1.4. ENLIGHT Workshop: “What makes Research Impact so Challenging? What can we do address these challenges? Good practices”

Taking advantage of the participation of ENLIGHT Impact Awards nominees, 2023 Impact Ambassadors, and FOREU2 impact experts (cfr. section 1.6) in the ENLIGHT Impact Event on 11 June 2024 in Bilbao, WP8 organised a workshop specifically targeted at discussing “What makes Research Impact so Challenging? What can we do to address these challenges? Good practices”.

Figure 10. Picture of the workshop “What makes Research Impact so Challenging? What can we do address these challenges? Good practices”.

Departing from the conclusions of 2023 Workshop on Barriers & Opportunities for Research Impact Driven Agendas², the 61 workshop participants discussed:

- In a first moment, and in 3 separate groups (researchers, University management staff, impact experts), the **CHALLENGES around research impact**. Question: “What makes Research Impact so Challenging for you?”
- In a second moment, in 10 mixed groups of 5-6 persons, **the SOLUTIONS and GOOD PRACTICES to address these challenges**. Question: “What can we do to address these challenges?”
- In a third moment, participants shared and contrasted the different solutions/ good practices.

The new identified challenges (i.e. impact suspicion and fatigue, temporality issue, academic freedom, stakeholder engagement related challenges) and proposed solutions and good practices will be detailed in section 2 and 3 of this report.

² Cfr. Deliverable 39

1.5. ENLIGHT Research Impact Training

On 22-23 May 2024, WP8 has launched its **first Research Impact Training targeting Research Support Officers of ENLIGHT Universities**. Counting with the participation of 12 in-person trainees and 20 online attendees, the main objective of the training was to empower ENLIGHT Research Support Officers to build their understanding and knowledge of impact, as well as competencies in supporting their research community. The training programme was designed to raise impact literacy and support skills development, with a specific focus on providing the tools and means for drafting the impact sections of Horizon Europe project proposals.

From the different training modules discussions, the conclusions session and the specific feedback survey, the training proved to be a **great opportunity to increase participants' research impact awareness** (*"Impact is really important"; "Impact is important not only for proposals, but also at institutional level"*) and **literacy** (*"improved understanding of impact pathway(s)"*). Besides, as challenge, participants highlighted the **difficulties to implement the lessons learnt at home universities** (*"there are many people in many roles that can help impact happen, but it requires a lot of commitment and resources"*). It is also worth highlighting a participant quote *"It's actually a challenge but I realised the need to prepare how to really explain in our cultural / institutional context the core of impact meaning and that is worth of trying. Even if it also means to accept that researcher should aim for something that is very much beyond their control (especially aiming for long-term change in current political and social context)"*.

1.6. FOREU2 Impact Thematic Group Meetings and Workshop

Led by the ENLIGHT Alliance, the FOREU2 impact thematic group was constituted in September 2022 with the following objectives:

- *Spread and share* approaches, solutions, successful practices, identified barriers and challenges, as well as cooperation formats and models;
- *Join efforts* in the way University Alliances address, measure and capture the impact and transformative effect on HEIs, on their local/regional ecosystem and on the European Higher Education and Research Areas;
- *Promote common approaches* for impact assessment and measurement;
- *Help University Alliances, and their individual HEIs, to embed impact* as an integral part of their strategic and operational actions; and
- Offer decision-makers at EU, national and regional levels, a sound, robust and joint *University Alliances' proposal for assessing and capturing their transformational effects on EHEA and ERA*.

Up to date (June 2024), the FOREU2 impact thematic group gathers **53 representatives of 23 FOREU2 University Alliances** (in August 2023 there were 37 representatives from 14 Alliances). Since its launch, **11 working meetings** have been organised in the context of the FOREU2 impact thematic group. Besides the discussion on topics of common interest (e.g. understanding of the concept of impact, monitoring framework for the European Universities Initiative), **11 University Alliances have presented their approach to impact, as well as the challenges, barriers and opportunities in relation to embedding impact** (CIRCLE U.; ENLIGHT, UNITA; ERUA; E³UDRES²; EC2U; ENHANCE; ULYSSEUS; EUT+; In-TUNE; U!REKA SHIFT).

Coinciding with the launch of the second phase of many of FOREU2 Alliances, in the 13 December 2023 meeting, FOREU2 members were invited to share their experiences and future action for the 2023-

2027 period. Besides, and as part of the ENLIGHT Impact Event organised on 11 June in Bilbao, WP8 organised a specific workshop with FOREU members to discuss the **different tools for impact assessment the Alliances are using**.

In the workshop, the challenges related to the understanding of the impact concept and its connections with quality assurance, as well as the importance of distinguishing between outputs, outcomes and impact terms were raised. Data collection related challenges and the difficulties to implement impact-direct management approaches at an Alliance level were also raised during the workshop. The use of AI and machine learning for impact monitoring was also presented as an opportunity in the context of impact monitoring and assessment.

2. Barriers and Opportunities for Research Impact-Driven Agendas

In this section we present the results of the analysis on the collected barriers, challenges, and opportunities to implement impact-driven research agendas during the period of September 2023 to August 2024. We consider barriers and opportunities for both impact-driven research agendas at universities institutional level, and for common impact-driven research agendas among different institutions.

Despite the **positive evolution in terms of both impact awareness** (i.e. understanding and internationalisation of the importance of research impact, external context and institutional commitment) **and impact literacy** (i.e. knowledge, competencies and skills), the analysis of the collected data shows that in general **2021-2023 identified barriers/ opportunities persist**. However, the WP8 team could obtain a **more detailed perspective of the identified barriers and opportunities per type of stakeholder** (research managers, impact experts, and researchers), as well as identify **new barriers and opportunities**.

2.1. Barriers and Challenges

Low Impact Literacy Levels

As regards the first identified barrier on low impact literacy levels, it was possible to observe that the majority of **ENLIGHT universities has now a definition of research impact or shares the definition provided by ENLIGHT RISE WP8** (cfr. results of the landscaping exercise and self-assessment toolkit). Even if there is not a single internationally accepted definition (it does not have to be the case either), **it is commonly accepted that research impact goes beyond scientific excellence, communication and societal engagement, and is different from performance and quality assurance**.

The barriers related to the low impact literacy levels are more specific and **related to the challenges in planning, monitoring, capturing, assessing and communicating research impact**. For example, researchers participating in the workshop *“what makes research impact so challenging”* have highlighted the difficulties in answering these questions:

- *What is the difference between outputs, outcomes and impact?*
- *How to value indirect impact(s)?*
- *How to classify the generated impacts?*
- *How to capture and assess impacts that occur in the medium to long-term?*

As CIRCLE U. presented during the FOREU2 Impact Thematic Workshop (11 June 2024), there are other particular challenges **related to impact monitoring, data collection and analysis**:

- *Difficulties in obtaining good quality, relevant, standardised data that is meaningful to show true progress and impact of activities.*
- *Collecting both good quality quantitative and qualitative data, coupled with survey fatigue and lack of data diversity.*
- *Tools that make data collection easier, not more difficult.*

Lack of Structures, Capacities and Resources

The organisational capacities and resources of a university drive its ability and readiness to deliver on its research impact strategy and commitment. Impact-related support and advice, systems, tools, funding, time, people, competencies, expertise and knowledge are all important conditions within a university for promoting and managing research impact.

The ENLIGHT Research Impact Landscaping exercise, as well as the self-assessment toolkit results have **shown important progress at ENLIGHT partner universities in terms of developing the structures and capacities for research impact**. In this context, it is worth mentioning University of Groningen's efforts in further developing the Research & Impact cluster in the last couple of years. Situated at the core of the university, the cluster contributes to university-wide policy, provides advice to the board and supports faculties and researchers. It is currently making an inventory of research impact practices across the different faculties. Likewise, at the University of the Basque Country a new Social Impact Office was created at the end of 2023 to spread impact culture throughout the university and is also conducting studies aiming at measuring the social impact of the university (cfr. section 1.1. for further ENLIGHT universities examples).

Despite these positive trends, **the lack of capacities and resources are still considered as a major barrier by researchers and research support staff** (cfr. section 1.2. on self-assessment toolkit results and the feedback on research impact training). In fact, the majority of ENLIGHT universities do not have dedicated systems (repositories, tools, platforms) for research impact; the majority of researchers and research support staff state not following a methodology for research impact; and only a small percentage of respondents (22%) agree that their university offers support training in research impact related skills. 42% of RSOs respondents state never having participated in research impact training. In fact, the toolkit results show that the provision of training for the development of research impact-related competences and skills is limited to a few ENLIGHT universities. A reality that seems to also be present beyond ENLIGHT universities, as discussions with EARMA impact thematic group have revealed.

The conclusions of the ENLIGHT Impact Event workshop also confirm that the lack of mechanisms around the implementation of research impact agendas is an important challenge, including a lack of funding and professional support, overall creating a barrier in promoting common research-impact driven agendas. As a representative of the research managers discussion group mentioned it: "which structure or who is going to track the impact of research, besides the researchers themselves?"

Low Commitment Levels: Lack of strategy, Leadership and Recognition for Research Impact

As highlighted in the 2023 report, the lack of capacities and resources for research impact at universities may be an indication of the absence of commitment with research impact, through the **lack of strategy, leadership and recognition**. A research impact-driven university assumes that there is commitment across the institution and at all levels of action. Commitment may take many forms. The most comprehensive approach would be the adoption of a research impact policy that underpins a strategic plan and is operationalized by an implementation plan that is adequately and appropriately resourced. However, this comprehensive approach is not a prerequisite for a committed research-impact driven university, but the support of institutional structures, policies and processes certainly is.

The self-assessment toolkit results (cfr. Section 1.2.) indicate that research impact is considered as a strategic priority by the majority of researchers (64%) and research support staff (92%) respondents. It also shows that 8/9 institutional responders say that the University will "greatly prioritise" around research impact in the coming 5 years, and that 7/9 recognise there is institutional leadership in research impact.

Despite these positive findings and trends, the self-assessment toolkit results, the participation in external events (such as the EARMA and UIIN conferences), and the ENLIGHT workshop "*what makes research impact so challenging*", have demonstrated three major interrelated barriers/ challenges when talking about low commitment levels:

- 1) **the lack of impact ecosystem at universities**. Researcher managers present at the ENLIGHT workshop indicate that commitment goes beyond having a research impact policy, requiring

also important changes across the whole institution (e.g. HR departments, communications, technology transfer, etc.). The commitment to impact should be shared across the different university structures, which is not always the case. In fact, there is a challenge in making the different structures understanding what is in it for them when embedding research impact at the university. As a trainee participating in the ENLIGHT Research Impact Training mentioned *“there are many people in many roles that can help impact happen, but it requires a lot of commitment and resources”*.

- 2) **the lack of connectivity at institutional level.** According to the self-assessment results, only 1/3 of researchers and RSOs respondents state they do work with other teams to support research impact, and 42% indicated that research impact activities are only “possibly/partly” aligned with the University’s strategy.
- 3) **the lack of reward systems, recognition and appreciation of research impact** has been highlighted repeatedly in the various sources of information. As already pointed out in the 2023 report, there are very few systems allowing and valorizing impact-driven research, in contrast to the focus on academic excellence (scientific impact). Similarly, traditional research career progression models do not explicitly recognise research impact work. The recognition and appreciation of impactful research is low in many cases. This lack of appreciation and recognition is also hindering the opportunities in developing common agendas, as the success stories are not being made visible and/or shared.

Context: Different Regional, National and Institutional Landscapes

In the 2023 report, WP8 team has identified the **differing regional, national and institutional research policies, funding, regulations, and legislation** as a major barrier, especially hindering the development of common research-impact driven agendas. In connection with this finding, the research managers participating in the workshop *“what makes research impact so challenging”* highlighted the contradictory or even incomplete Higher Education and Research strategies at local, regional and national levels.

In the same workshop, research managers also mentioned the different **“fashions” in societal challenges**, with the interpretation of the societies’ problems differing in function of changing political agendas.

It is worth highlighting the 2023 findings on the **diversity across European universities in the context of culture and language, and the competitive nature of research and competition between universities** as barriers in creating meaningful collaboration and a common impact-driven research agenda.

This is directly linked to the **differing research impact cultures among European universities**, further accentuated by the **distinct approaches to impact from the different fields of knowledge and disciplines** (social sciences, natural sciences, formal sciences or applied sciences). The differing disciplines approaches was actually mentioned by the impact experts participating in the workshop *“what makes research impact so challenging”*. More specifically, as highlighted by the research managers group, and also in the context of Galway’s Research Impact Series, *“the focus on societal relevance makes basic researchers don’t feeling part of the impact conversation”*.

Other challenges: Impact suspicion and fatigue, temporality, academic freedom, stakeholder engagement related challenges

During the last 12 months, ENLIGHT RISE WP8 could also identify new barriers and challenges to the establishment of research impact-driven agendas. The relaunch of the spring 2022 impact survey through the self-assessment toolkit in 2024 has demonstrated a decrease in the level of responses by ENLIGHT university staff, which denoted a **certain survey and/or impact fatigue**. This observation was confirmed by colleagues from other European University Alliances during the FOREU2 Impact Thematic Group workshop (11 June 2024), who are facing similar challenges in data collection and impact assessment exercises.

Linked to this finding, it is important to highlight a certain **suspicion around research impact and the research impact agenda**, which we believe is an effect of other barriers already identified (e.g. low impact literacy and low commitment levels, etc.)

During the workshop on *“what makes research so challenging”*, impact experts and research managers also mentioned the **“temporality” nature of impact as a specific challenge**. On the one side, impact experts recognise that impact monitoring and assessment is time consuming, and mention the difficulties to assess impacts that occur in the medium to long-term. On the other side, research managers mention that *“everyone”* has different timelines, which puts extra pressure on the academic community. In fact, there are the funding authorities reporting obligations, universities' reporting demands, and research projects' own timeline, not all coinciding at the same moment and creating an extra burden for the academic community.

Academic freedom and the independence of academic work and schools/ faculties was also highlighted by the workshop research managers group as a challenge to develop meaningful collaboration and implement an institutional impact-driven research agenda.

Another challenge specifically raised by the researchers and impact experts participating in the workshop on *“what makes research so challenging”*, is the **complexity of the processes to involve different stakeholders in research projects**, as well as **to take into consideration their often “unrealistic” expectations**.

2.2 Opportunities

The 2023 analysis (cfr. Deliverable 39) has identified as opportunities for impact-driven research agendas:

- The favourable momentum
- Connectivity among university teams
- Co-creation with societal stakeholders
- Available capacities and resources
- ENLIGHT leadership and platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration

All these elements remain as key opportunities and drivers for impact-driven research agendas. However, during the last year, WP8 team has observed new trends and opportunities that may contribute to the further advancement of impact in our Research & Innovation ecosystem(s).

In the last year, the WP8 team has seen the raise of **Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a technology that could offer assistance in the performance and implementation of impact-related tasks**. Several examples of machine learning and AI technologies application in the revision of impact sections of grants proposals, in the data treatment or drafting of impact cases studies/ narratives have been shared during the EARMA and UIIN conferences above mentioned, as well as by UNITA University Alliance. However, its potential use is not exempt of challenges and risks that we should be aware of, such as: ensuring the confidentiality and protection of research data, the risk of perpetuating/ amplifying existing biases and not being fair; the interpretability of large amounts of data; ethical concerns, including the potential for misuse; etc.

In connection to the “favourable momentum” opportunity, it was possible to observe that **the topic of “impact” is present and covered in all the different sessions of the wider thematically focused Conferences** of EARMA (Odense, April 2024) or UIIN (Madrid, May 2024). The establishment and further working advancements of the **EARMA impact thematic group** and the links established with the ENLIGHT RISE WP8 team in the last year is also an opportunity we wish to further exploit. Likewise, **ENLIGHT is strengthening its working connections with other international networks**, such as the UIIN (joint proposals for EU-funding have been presented) or AESIS networks.

The possibility of establishing the FOREU2 impact thematic group and enlarging its membership to all European Universities Alliances in the **framework of the future FOREU4ALL project** is also an opportunity ENLIGHT intends to capitalize on. It represents a great opportunity to spread and share approaches, solutions, successful practices as well as cooperation formats and models for research-impact driven agendas, creating thus a community of University Alliances around impact and increasing the potential for common impact-driven research agendas.

In alignment with the 2023 opportunity “*ENLIGHT leadership and platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration*”, it is worth highlighting **ENLIGHT efforts to foster a culture of impact in and beyond ENLIGHT**. The ENLIGHT 2.0 project, through its ENLIGHT Impact Taskforce and planned activities will certainly be a key driver for promoting impact-driven agendas at our Universities. At this respect, the organisation of **biennial international impact conferences**, the **impact awards** to recognize and give visibility to impactful practices in global higher education, and the **ENLIGHT training and mentoring** for academics and early career researchers are some of the initiatives that our communities could benefit from. Coupled with the future establishment of the **ENLIGHT Expert Network on Research Impact** for knowledge sharing, exchange of good practices and advice, ENLIGHT is providing the support to the development of impact-driven universities.

3. Solutions and Good Practices

The ENLIGHT workshop “*What makes Research Impact so Challenging? What can we do to address these challenges? Good practices*” gave participants the opportunity to discuss not only challenges, but also to jointly identify potential solutions and good practices to those challenges. The ten groups were given the leeway to choose and address the barriers/challenges they wanted to. These were:

Low Impact Literacy Levels

Solutions:

- **Change the narrative around research impact**, translating and explaining the impact jargon to and in function of the different university structures and stakeholders (make them understand what is in it for them)
- University systems and staff use **the “right” language**
- **More courses and training in research impact as early as possible**, as a starting point
- **Use the potential of “role-models” and mentors**, as complementary to training
- Recognise that **researchers can’t be experts on everything**.

Good Practices:

- Existing training and courses on Research Impact, but only as a starting point.
- ENLIGHT workshops, training, and toolkits.

Low Commitment Levels: Lack of strategy, Leadership and Recognition for Research Impact

Solutions:

- Beyond the University: a European document outlining broad guiding principles for research impact
- Within the University:
 - o Raise awareness of impact as a common good and part of the University mission
 - o Develop co-creative impact decisions, discussions and definitions
 - o Invest in the structures required to facilitate meaningful impact (e.g. impact officers, communication staff)
 - o Use “carrots” not “sticks”
 - o Making impact visible, going beyond academic papers, and building upon the potential of public engagement (e.g. festivals) and communication tools (e.g. podcasts, public interviews, etc.)
 - o Embed “impact” where necessary and applicable (taking into consideration that it is context specific), including the academics workload and career trajectories
 - o “Impact” is included into the promotion system
- Individual level: everyone accepts that there is no single and clear definition of what it means to be impactful and that this is ok.

Good Practices:

- Presence of dedicated impact officers (at central and faculty levels)
- The position of “impact professor” at the University of Groningen
- Public recognition of research impact stories
- Ghent University evaluation system and new progression model, which rewards impact activity.

Specifically, on Rewards and Recognition related challenges

Solutions: Develop a system that:

- Combines a holistic with an individualised approach
- Without checklists and quantitative assessments
- Provides more support if there is external funding
- Empowers pre- and post-doc researchers
- Make it part of both the hiring and promotion systems.

This system developed in the academic context, should be coupled with an “economical model” by public authorities that rewards more than academic outputs.

“Temporality” nature of impact

Solutions:

- Providing institutional support, infrastructure and resources
- Increase impact literacy, trough tools and best practices sharing
- Recognise and reward academics efforts and impactful research, for example through promotion and awards. This would ensure ownership and accountability in impact assessment

Good Practices:

3. ENLIGHT repository of good practices on research impact
4. ENLIGHT impact awards
5. University of Galway Research Impact Toolkit.

Unrealistic stakeholders’ expectations

Solutions:

- Define well in advance the target group(s) of the research initiative in order to get insights
- Exchange, contrast and identify the different target groups’ needs and expectations
- Provide realistic outcomes and communicate them.

As can be observed, not all challenges have been addressed by the workshop group discussions. This may be an indication that participants have no solutions/good practices to propose to address those challenges, or that those challenges are not considered as relevant as the ones they decided to discuss. The proposed solutions and good practices represent a good source of inspiration for future action by our ENLIGHT community, which will be taken into consideration in the framework of ENLIGHT 2.0 project, the future ENLIGHT Expert Networks, and the FOREU4ALL project.

Looking ahead

As previously highlighted, the efforts deployed by ENLIGHT RISE WP8 team **to foster a culture of research impact within and beyond the alliance**, helping addressing the identified barriers and challenges and capitalising on the identified opportunities will continue beyond the RISE project. For that purpose, most of WP8 team members will continue to work together in the **framework of ENLIGHT 2.0 Impact Task Force**, which has committed to:

- *Upgrade the ENLIGHT methodological framework and toolkit for impact assessment of Higher Education Activities*
- *Keep on liaising with other international networks working on impact matters and leading the FOREU Impact Thematic Group to share good practices and promote a culture of impact-direct management*
- *Organise biennial international Impact Conferences*
- *Launch new calls for Impact Awards and nominate the ENLIGHT Impact Ambassadors with the purpose of recognising and giving visibility to impactful best practices in global higher education*
- *Organise training and mentoring for academics and early career researchers, helping them build robust impact pathways for both education and research and innovation activities whilst contributing to raising impact literacy and readiness.*

In parallel, the future **ENLIGHT Expert Network on Research Impact** will be constituted as a community of practice for the informal exchange of good practices, mutual learning, exchange of information about research impact, providing support and advice to ENLIGHT 2.0 Impact Task Force when deemed appropriate.